

CONTRIBUTING INSTITUTES AND MODELS OF THE MED-CORDEX BASELINE RUNS

version 0: S. Somot, January 2020

version 1: S. Somot, March 2021

version 2: S. Somot, Oct 2021, merging Phase 1 and Phase 2 run lists

version 3: S. Somot, Feb 2022, last update

version 4: S. Somot, April 2022, creation of the model list used for the Med-CORDEX phase 3 baseline runs. I keep in the list all the coupled models ever developed in Med-CORDEX, indicating in 'Status' in which phases they have been used.

version 5: S. Somot, 26 Sept 2022, first official list, posted on zenodo

version 6: S. Somot, 12 May 2023, various changes in preparation of the Med-CORDEX workshop

version 7: S. Somot, 1 Aug 2023, changes with the info from Med-CORDEX workshop, posted on zenodo

Version 8: S. Somot, 13 June 2024, changes after the Med-CORDEX workshop, posted on zenodo

Version 9: S. Somot, I. Parras-Berrocal, 20 april 2026, reorganise the list in 2 sections (CORDEX-CMIP5 and CORDEX-CMIP6) and update the model names to match with the literature and official IPCC Interactive Atlas and CORDEX github naming

In Med-CORDEX, 21 different RCSMs (coupled Regional Climate System Models) have been developed and used so far by 11 different institutes. This includes phase 1, phase 2 and phase 3 models; phase 3 corresponding to the latest model version.

Color Code: **Model ready**, **Model under development**, **Institute interested by the initiative**

Med-CORDEX-CMIP6 Contributing Institutes and Models (Med-CORDEX Phase 3 baseline runs)

Model Naming, <i>source_id</i>	Institute, <i>institution_id</i>	Contact	Climate components	Model short description	Model status and last update
CNRM-RC6SM6-SN	CNRM	S. Somot, F. Sevault	Atmosphere Aerosols Land (incl. Lake, underground waters) River Ocean	Atmosphere:ALADIN6.4@12km, Aerosol:TACTIC@12km, Land-Surface:SURFEX8@12km (incl. lake), SurfHydrology:CTRIPv2@50km, Ocean:NEMOv3.6-MED12-75L@7km, Coupler: OASIS-MCT@1hour, <i>Ref: Darmaraki et al. 2019b, Nabat et al. 2020, Sevault 2024</i>	Ready, April 2022
CNRM-RC6SM6B-SN	CNRM	S. Somot, F. Sevault, P. Nabat	Atmosphere Aerosols Land (incl. Lake, underground waters) River Ocean	Atmosphere:ALADIN6.5.1@12km, Aerosol:TACTIC@12km, Land-Surface:SURFEX8@12km (incl. lake), SurfHydrology:CTRIPv2@10km, Ocean:NEMOv3.6-MED12-75L@7km, Coupler:OASIS-MCT@1hour, <i>Ref: Nabat et al. 2020, Sevault et al. in prep.</i>	Ready, April 2026
ENEA-REG2	ENEA	G. Sannino A. Anav MV. Struglia A.Dell'Aquila	Atmosphere Land River Ocean	including WRF (12km, 51L), surface: NOAA-MP, MedMIT (1/12°, 75L), HD (0.5°), RegESM as coupler, 3hourly coupling frequency <i>Ref: Anav et al. 2021</i>	Ready, May 2023
ENEA-REG3	ENEA	G. Sannino A. Anav MV. Struglia A.Dell'Aquila	Atmosphere Land River Ocean	including WRF (12km, 51L), surface: NOAA-MP, MedMIT (1/12°, 75L), CaMaflood v4.11 (5.5 km), RegESM as coupler, 3hourly coupling frequency <i>Ref:</i>	Ready, July 2025
CCLM5-0-9-NEMOMED1 2-3-6	CLMcom-GUF	B. Ahrens P. Kumar M. Hamouda	Atmosphere Land River Ocean	including COSMO-CLMv5.00clm9 (12km), NEMOv3.6-MED12, CTRIP, OASIS3-MCT3.0 (1h) <i>Ref: Primo et al. 2019</i>	Ready, Jan 2024

ICON-CLM / ICON-O-LAM or ICON-XPP	CLMcom-GUF	B. Ahrens	Atmosphere Land River Ocean	Including ICON-CLM / ICON-O-LAM or ICON-XPP <i>Ref:</i>	Under development, May 2024
LMDZ4NEMOMED8v2, also called LMDZ-MEDv2	LMD	L. Li	Atmosphere Land River Ocean	including LMDZ4@30km (MED-25), ORCHIDEE@30km, NEMOMED8, simple river coupling scheme <i>Ref:</i>	Ready, Jan 2024
RegIPSLv2	IPSL	J. Polcher R. Pennel	Atmosphere Land River Ocean	including WRF4.2@12km@50levels (Euro-CORDEX domain), ORCHIDEEv4 incl. Flood plains, water river temperature, dam, reservoirs, irrigation, CO2, nitrate, transport, NEMO4-MED36?, OASIS-MCT@1h, option Eco3M in dvt. No CHIMERE <i>Ref:</i>	Under development, May 2023
MedESM	CMCC	S. Gualdi	Atmosphere Land River Ocean	Including WRF@12km, CLM5@1/12° (lake, glacier, urban, ...), HYDROS@1/12°, NEMO4.2-MFS@1/16° (incl. Black Sea), CICE6@1/16°, (BFM@1/16° in option), Cime/Nuopc as coupler/driver	Under development, May 2024
EBUPOM2e	UBEL	V. Djurdjevic	Atmosphere Land Ocean River	Including EBU@12km/L48 (Eta Belgrade University), POM@10km/L??, air-sea coupling is hard-coded, river coupling included (under testing)	Under development, May 2023
RegESM ???	ITU	B. Onol	Atmosphere Land Ocean xxx	RegESM with WRF instead of RegCM, MITgcm instead of ROMS, HD for river	Interested, April 2022
ROM22	AWI	W. Cabos D. Sein	Atmosphere Land River Ocean	including REMO@12km, MPIOM(variable from 3 to 12km), HD, OASIS <i>Ref: Sein et al. 2015</i>	Interested, Nov 2024
RegCM-ES1-1	ICTP	E. Coppola G.Giuliani	Atmosphere Land River	including RegCM5@12km, CLM4.5, MITgcm 1/12° 75L (Black Sea explicit), CHyM@7km <i>Ref: Reale et al., 2020</i>	Ready, March 2025

			Ocean		
ICON-OASIS-NEMO	CLMcom-IMS	P. Khain L. Uzan E. Vadsilavsky	Atmosphere Land Ocean	Including ICON-CLM@12km, NEMO3.6-MED12v75, OASIS	Under development, May 2024
MedX-CM	NKUA	J. Karagiorgos	Atmosphere Land River Ocean Waves Biogeochemistry	Atmosphere: WRF-v4.3.3@12km, 45L Ocean: NEMO-v4.2.0@1/12°, 50L (explicit Black Sea) Land: Noah-MP (incl. in WRF)@12km River: HD-v5.1 (under dev) @1/12° Waves: WW3-v6.07@1/12° (common grid with NEMO) ? Biogeo.: PISCES-v4.0 (incl. in NEMO; under tuning) Coupler: OASIS3-MCT-v4.0@1hr (higher freq for wave cpl) <i>Ref: Karagiorgos et al., 2024, 2025</i>	Under development, June 2025
ICON-ESM	CLMcom-CMCC	A. Campanale	Atmosphere Ocean	Atmosphere: ICON Ocean: ICON-O	Under development, June 2025

Med-CORDEX-CMIP5 Contributing Institutes and Models (Med-CORDEX Phase 1 and Phase 2 baseline runs)

Model Naming, <i>model_id</i>	Institute, <i>institute_id</i>	Contact	Climate components	Model short description	Phases
RCSM4	CNRM	S. Somot, F. Sevault	Atmosphere Land River Ocean	Atmosphere: ALADIN5 @50km, Land-surface: ISBA @50km, River: CTRIP @50km, Ocean: NEMOMED8 @9-12km, coupler: OASIS @1day, <i>Ref: Sevault et al. 2014</i>	Phase 1 Phase 2
RCSM6 also called CNRM-RCSM6 or CNRM-RCSM6-SN	CNRM	S. Somot, F. Sevault, P. Nabat	Atmosphere Aerosols Land (incl. Lake, underground waters) River Ocean	Atmosphere: ALADIN6 @12km, Aerosol: TACTIC @12km, Land-Surface: SURFEX8 @12km (incl. lake), SurfHydrology: CTRIPv2 @50km, Ocean: NEMOv3.6-MED12-75L @7km, coupler: OASIS-MCT @1hour, <i>Ref: Darmaraki et al. 2019b, Nabat et al. 2020, Sevault 2024</i> http://www.umr-cnrm.fr/spip.php?article1098	Phase 2
PROTHEUSv2	ENEA	A. Dell'Aquila	Atmosphere Land River Ocean	30km	Phase 1 Phase 2
RegCM-ES	ENEA	G. Sannino	Atmosphere Land River Ocean	including RegCM4.5 (20km), MedMIT at 1/12°, HD, ESMF as coupler 3hourly or 1hourly <i>Ref:</i>	Phase 2
CCLM-NEMO	CLMcom-GUF	B. Ahrens	Atmosphere Land Ocean	including COSMO-CLMv5.00clm9 (50km), NEMOv3.6-MED12,	Phase 1 Phase 2
CCLM5-0-9-NEMOMED12 -3-6	CLMcom-GUF	B. Ahrens P. Kumar M. Hamouda	Atmosphere Land River Ocean	including COSMO-CLMv5.00clm9 (12km), NEMOv3.6-MED12, CTRIP, OASIS3-MCT3.0 (1h) <i>Ref: Primo et al. 2019</i>	Phase 2

LMDZ4-NEMOMED8v1, also called LMDZ-MEDv1	LMD	L. Li	Atmosphere Land Ocean	including LMDZ4@30km, ORCHIDEE@30km, NEMOMED8, no river coupling, <i>Ref: L'Hévéder et al. 2013</i>	Phase 1
LMDZ4-NEMOMED8v2, also called LMDZ-MEDv2	LMD	L. Li	Atmosphere Land River Ocean	including LMDZ4@30km (MED-25), ORCHIDEE@30km, NEMOMED8, simple river coupling scheme <i>Ref:</i>	Phase 2
MORCEMED	IPSL	S. Bastin	Atmosphere Land Ocean	WRF311@20km , NEMOMED12	Phase 1
RegIPSL	IPSL	J. Polcher R. Pennel	Atmosphere Land River Ocean	including WRF.3.7.1@20km-46L, ORCHIDEE@20km, NEMOMED12-75L OASIS-MCT@1h <i>Ref:</i>	Phase 2
CCLM4-21-NEMOMFSv1 (50km), also called COSMOMED	CMCC	L. Cavicchia P. Lionello S. Gualdi	Atmosphere Land Ocean	COSMO-CLM v4.21 at 50km and 45L, Nemo_MFS v4.3 at 7km, 71L, OASIS3-MCT (no river coupling)	Phase 1 Phase 2
CCLM4-21-NEMOMFSv2 (12km), also called COSMOMED	CMCC	D. Conte P. Lionello L. Cavicchia S. Gualdi	Atmosphere Land Ocean	including COSMO-CLM v4.21 at 12km and 45L, TERRA, Nemo_MFS v4.3 at 1/16°, 71L, OASIS3-MCT (no river coupling) <i>Ref: Cavicchia et al. 2015, Conte et al. 2020</i>	Phase 1 Phase 2
EBUPOM2c	UBEL	V. Djurdjevic	Atmosphere Land Ocean	Including EBU@50km/L32 (Eta Belgrade University), POM@30km/L21, air-sea coupling is hard-coded at 6 min (no river coupling) <i>Ref:</i>	Phase 1 Phase 2
RegESM1	ITU	B. Onol F. Batibeniz	Atmosphere Land Ocean	including RegCM4-6-0@50km	Phase 1 Phase 2
RegESM1.2	ITU	B. Onol F. Batibeniz	Atmosphere Land Ocean	including RegCM4-6-0@12km, ROMSr809@9km, WAM.4@14km (no river coupling in this configuration but this can be activated using RTM module from MPI). 1hr-coupling frequency <i>Ref: Turuncoglu and Sannino (2017), Turuncoglu (2019), Batibeniz et al.</i>	Phase 1 Phase 2

				(2025)	
ROM44	AWI-GERICS	W. Cabos D. Sein	Atmosphere Land River Ocean	including REMO@25km, MPIOM(variable from 20 to 7km), HD, OASIS Ref: Sein et al. 2015	Phase 1 Phase 2
ROM22	AWI-GERICS	W. Cabos D. Sein	Atmosphere Land River Ocean	including REMO@25km, MPIOM(variable from 20 to 7km), HD, OASIS Ref: Sein et al. 2015	Phase 1 Phase 2
ROM11	AWI-GERICS	W. Cabos D. Sein	Atmosphere Land River Ocean	including REMO@12km, MPIOM(variable from 3 to 12km), HD, OASIS Ref: Sein et al. 2015	Phase 1 Phase 2
ROMS-MED	INSTM-LMD	A. Harzallah	Atmosphere Land Ocean	including LMDZ4 and ROMS-MED	Phase 1

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